

COMPUTER-AIDED DETECTION OF SCLEROTIC BONE METASTASES IN THE SPINE USING WATERSHED ALGORITHM AND SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINES

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a computer-aided detection (CAD) system to aid radiologists in finding sclerotic bone metastases in the spine on CT images. The spine is first segmented using thresholding, region growing and a vertebra template. A watershed algorithm and a merging routine segment potential lesion candidates in each two-dimensional (2-D) axial CT image. Next, overlapping 2-D detections on sequential CT slices are merged to form 3-D candidate lesions. For each of these, 30 quantitative features based on shape, density, and location are computed. After a feature filter eliminates clearly false candidates, a ground truth on 10 clinical cases segmented manually by an expert, and the features of each CAD candidate are used to train seven support vector machines. The segmentation algorithm detects 164 out of the 212 manually segmented lesions. A ten-fold cross-validation trained on these detections results in 77.4% sensitivity at an average of 9.44 false positives per case.

Index Terms— computer aided detection, bone metastasis, sclerotic lesion

1. INTRODUCTION

Bone metastases are significantly associated with cancer, with occurrence in up to 70% of people afflicted with advanced prostate and breast cancer. Approximately 350,000 people in the United States die with bone metastases each year [1]. The tumor burden at the time of death in patients with advanced breast or prostate cancer is likely to be mostly in bone for reasons including the high blood flow in red marrow regions, the angiogenic and bone-resorbing factors produced by tumor cells when they bind to stromal cells in the marrow and to the bone matrix, and immobilized growth factors in the bone that help the tumor cells grow [1]. The morbidity is often debilitating: bone metastases can result in severe bone pain, pathological fractures often in load-bearing bones, and spinal cord and other nerve compression [1]. Moreover, no more than 20% of breast cancer patients survive more than five years after the initial discovery of the metastasis [1]. Thus the early detection of bone metastases has significant clinical importance. For example in the case of prostate cancer, the prognosis and treatment regime for the patient changes from curative to palliative when prostate tumor cells are discovered in the skeleton [1]. The spine is an essential support structure for the upper body and plays an indispensable part in protecting the spinal cord. Therefore we begin our study of bone metastases with the spine.

The broadest classification of bone metastases based on the radiographic and tomographic appearance consists of osteolytic (also known as lytic) and osteoblastic (also known as sclerotic) metastases. Osteolytic metastases are characterized by decreased bone density due to the destruction of bone tissue, whereas sclerotic metastases consist of hyperdense bone regions [1]. An example of each is shown in Figure 1. Generally, a cancer patient with osseous metastatic disease may present with either type of lesion, and the metastases can be predominantly lytic or predominantly sclerotic depending on the type of cancer. For example, metastases caused by breast cancer are usually lytic, whereas metastases caused by prostate cancer are usually sclerotic [1]. Sclerotic lesions are believed to be caused by the production of growth factors that encourage osteoblast proliferation, differentiation, and bone formation [1]. A similar study to this one, which presents a CAD system for detecting lytic bone lesions in the spine, has been previously conducted [2]. Our purpose is to expand upon this study by developing CAD software for the detection of sclerotic osseous metastases in the spine, as an initial foray into a broader study of computational analysis of neoplastic and traumatic bone lesions.

Fig. 1. Thoracic spine showing a) sclerotic lesion; b) lytic lesion.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD OVERVIEW

A series of CT scans from 10 patients with studies demonstrating sclerotic metastatic disease in the spine was gathered. The slice thickness was 5mm. A total of 212 lesions were identified, marked, and manually segmented by an expert radiologist. Lesion volumes ranged from 44.4 mm³ to 52,700 mm³. There were 8 patients (80%) with prostate cancer, one patient (10%) with lung cancer, and one patient (10%) with breast cancer. The cases were obtained from an electronic medical record search of the NIH Clinical Center in the period July 2009-2010. The patient age ranged from 50-75 years, with an average of 64.6 years.

Our approach to the process of computer-aided lesion detection consists of three general steps: 1) segmentation of anatomic structures of interest (in this case, the spine), as well as

Fig.2. Flow chart of method.

lesion candidates, from background structures, 2) a training step of ten-fold cross-validation on the ten cases, and 3) a testing step performed again via ten-fold cross-validation on the ten cases. The training and testing steps involve the same steps of candidate and feature extraction followed by preliminary filtering based on the features. Figure 2 shows the flow chart of our method. We analyze the results of the SVM classifier by plotting a free-response receiver operating characteristic (FROC) curve depicting sensitivities and false positive rates.

3. PRE-PROCESSING

We used a spine segmentation algorithm developed in a previous study [2]. After segmenting and localizing the spine via thresholding and region growing, we extract the spinal canal using a directed graph search on all the potential candidates: a directed acyclic graph $G(N,A)$ is constructed in which the nodes N are the canal candidates, and the edges A connect two nodes on adjacent slices. Each edge is given a weight based on overlap, and finally the longest path through the graph is computed with a directed graph searching algorithm and taken to be the spinal canal. This method avoids misclassifying lytic bone metastases or regions caused by partial volume of inter-vertebral discs as the spinal canal [2]. The vertebra borders are further refined using a vertebra template.

The spine region is then separated into cancellous bone, characterized by lower density (and so resultant lower image intensity), and cortical bone, which has a higher density and occurs mostly around the spine border. The vertebrae are also partitioned, marking regions that belong to intervertebral disk space which cannot contain any lesions. Since both sclerotic lesions and cortical bone demonstrate a high image intensity, we perform an erosion procedure on the spine border to avoid classifying cortical border regions as sclerotic lesions, and treat these regions separately from the interior body of the spine for the duration of the watershed and merging steps.

4. BONE METASTASIS DETECTION

After the spine segmentation and pre-processing stage is complete, we extract potential sclerotic bone metastases. First a watershed algorithm is applied to extract candidates, followed by a merging routine to avoid oversegmentation. The resulting 2-D candidates are then merged into 3-D "blobs". For each 3-D candidate, a set of features is computed and passed through a filter. The remaining candidates are then used to either train a committee of SVM's, or classified by the existing SVM's as true positive or false positive, depending on whether we are in the training stage or in the testing stage.

4.1. Watershed algorithm

The watershed algorithm views the gradient of the image intensity as a topographic surface [3]. Thus regions where the intensity is changing rapidly will have a greater "height" than regions in which intensities are gradually or barely changing. Regions around the border of a lesion have a high gradient and will therefore be the highest points in a watershed interpretation. The precise extraction of the borders can be described by the analogy of puncturing a hole in each local minimum of the watershed surface and slowly submerging it in a pool of water, building "dams" (watershed lines) wherever the water from two different basins would join. The watershed lines delimit relatively homogeneous regions of the image called catchment basins. Some of these catchment basins will be candidates for sclerotic lesions.

A major problem with the watershed method is oversegmentation [3]. That is, the catchment basins derived from the algorithm are too differentiated, and a true region of interest might be covered by multiple watershed regions. This can be due to noise, or due to the extraction of objects that are not being considered by the particular study. We deal with this by implementing a merging routine after the watershed segmentation. To begin, we rule out any region that does not fall into the segmented spine. Then:

- 1) Make a list of neighbors $N_k = \{n_i, i \in \{0, 1, \dots, m_k-1\}\}$ of each candidate k , where m_k is the number of neighbors of k .
- 2) Repeat for set number of iterations (we chose 4):
 - a) Repeat for each candidate k :
 - i) Determine the highest-intensity neighbor $n_{k, hi}$, where $I(k)$ is the average intensity of the detection k .
 - ii) For each neighbor n_i , evaluate the following conditions:
 - 1) The difference of average intensities $|I(k) - I(n_i)|$ is less than a threshold $6T$ (we chose $T = 10$) if $n_i = n_{k, hi}$, or $|I(k) - I(n_i)| < 4T$ if $n_i \neq n_{k, hi}$
 - 2) $|stdev(I(k)) - stdev(I(n_i))| < 50$, or $|I(k) - I(n_i)| < 3T$ and $n_i = n_{k, hi}$, where $stdev(I(k))$ is the standard deviation of intensity within the detection k .
 - 3) Either both k and n_i lie primarily ($>75\%$) on the cortical border of the disk, or neither of them do
 - 4) For each neighbor $n_j \in N_{n_i}$, $I(k) - I(n_j) > T/2$ or $|I(k) - I(n_j)| > 10T$, or $|I(k) - I(n_i)| < T$ and at least one of the candidates is very small
 - 5) Neither $area(k) < 5area(n_i)$ nor $area(n_i) < 5area(k)$, or $|I(k) - I(n_i)| < 125$
 - iii) If any of the conditions are false, go to the next k , unless both $I(k) > 1600$ and $I(n_i) > 1600$.
 - iv) If all of the conditions are true or both have intensity greater than 1600 , merge k and n_i into a single candidate.

This routine ensures that two candidates are only merged if they are similar in intensity and not too disproportionate in size unless they are very similar in intensity. Moreover, a candidate in

the cortical border is not merged with a candidate inside the noncortical disk. Finally, neither of them have other neighbors also similar in intensity which have a higher absolute intensity. The latter requirement is important because we are interested in the highest-intensity regions, so they have a higher priority when it comes to being merged, as long as the difference of intensities is still reasonably small. The particular conditions were established by trial and error. Figure 3 demonstrates the effect of the watershed merging routine. We can see that if the merger is not applied, only a small piece of the lesion is identified because the image was oversegmented.

Fig.3. Watershed merging routine. a) Original image. b) Detection if merging routine is applied. c) Detection if merging routine is not applied. d) Watershed segmentation before merging. e) Watershed segmentation after merging.

4.2. Merging into three dimensions

So far, the candidates are all two-dimensional. Of course, lesions actually extend through the spine in three dimensions. Therefore the next step is to merge the two-dimensional candidates that belong to the same lesion into a single three-dimensional "blob". Two candidates A and B are merged if and only if

- 1) they lie in adjacent slices z and $z+1$
- 2) for all 2-D candidates C on $slice(z+1)$ and all D on $slice(z)$, it is true that
$$\frac{(pr_A(B)/a(A)+pr_B(A)/a(B))/2}{(pr_A(C)/a(A)+pr_C(A)/a(C))/2}$$
and
$$\frac{(pr_A(B)/a(A)+pr_B(A)/a(B))/2}{(pr_D(B)/a(D)+pr_B(D)/a(B))/2}$$
where $slice(z)$ is the CT slice at height z , $pr_X(Y)$ is the fraction of candidate Y that overlaps with X when projected into the slice of X , and $a(X)$ is the area of candidate X . In other words, the average projectional overlap of A and B is greater than the average projectional overlap of A with any other candidate in the same slice as B , and also greater than the average projectional overlap of B with any candidate in the same slice as A .
- 3) $|I(A)-I(B)| < 300$, or $(pr_A(B)/a(A)+pr_B(A)/a(B))/2 > 0.6$ and there is less than 50% intervertebral space in the slice. This intensity threshold is much larger than the ones employed in the watershed merging routine because "adjacent" CT slices are actually 5mm apart, so there is more space for inhomogeneities within the lesions to manifest themselves. Also, lesions cannot appear in the intervertebral space.

4.3. Feature Computation and Filters

Next, a set of 30 features based on shape, intensity, and location is computed. These features characterize and distinguish true lesions

from false positives and were adapted from a set of similar features characterizing two-dimensional slices of lytic lesions. The shape features are derived from the spatial moments, the density features from the statistical moments of the intensity histogram, and the location features from the relative coordinates to the center of the spinal canal of the detection [2].

In the training phase, these quantities are used to train a committee of SVM's to judge the probability that a candidate in the testing set is a true positive based on how its features compare to those of the training set [4]. However, the large number of detections by the watershed algorithm alone would reduce the performance of the classifier. Therefore, a set of preliminary filters based on observations of typical bone metastases is applied to the detections. Some examples of detections these filters would exclude are:

- Too small: the number of pixels in detection is less than 5, or surface area less than 10 mm^2 , or volume less than 45 mm^3
- The detection is in the spinal process
- The shape is too elongated and close to the border--artifact of intervertebral space
- The centroid of the detection does not lie in the detection--irregular (nonconvex) shape
- Small (surface area $< 10 \text{ mm}^2$) and close to the spinal cord
- The intensity is $> 2300 \text{ HU}$ or $< 1200 \text{ HU}$
- The contrast with average neighbor intensity is less than 150 HU

5. CLASSIFICATION

It is difficult to put down a hard set of rules that filters out all false positives and lets the true detections through for any given case. Parameter values that optimize the results for one case are not necessarily optimal for another, and so may exclude true positives if the filter is made too specific (high variance). On the other hand, if the filter is too general there will be too many false positives (high bias). A solution to this tradeoff arising from statistical learning theory is the Support Vector Machine (SVM), which minimizes the combined sources of error by nonlinearly mapping the feature vectors into a high-dimensional space in which they can be separated by a hyperplane [4].

To further reduce the complexity, we train seven SVM's on different three-dimensional feature-vector subspaces chosen using the training data to compute the separating plane in hyperspace. The subspaces are chosen by a progressive feature vector selector which is optimized by a two-way ANOVA analysis [4]. Each SVM computes an individual score for a given candidate, and then a majority vote determines the final score. This way we can use a large number of features without making the feature space for a single SVM too large.

6. VALIDATION METHODS

To validate the results of the SVM classifier, we performed a FROC (Free-response receiver operating characteristic) analysis. A FROC curve plots the number of false positives per image against the sensitivity as some parameter is varied [5]. In this case we vary the cutoff score c at which the SVM's start classifying detections as false positives rather than true positives. Figure 4 shows the FROC curve for our algorithm.

The SVM was only presented with 164 out of the 212 lesions because the feature filter eliminated some true detections. This is due in part to a weakness in the watershed merging algorithm: there is no setting of intensity and size thresholds in the rules that is optimal for every case. Current work involves improving the versatility of the algorithm by using more sophisticated segmentation methods such as graph cuts. Other reasons for missed lesions include insufficient intensity contrast of the lesion with the surrounding osseous material, which could thwart the watershed algorithm.

The total number of false positives per case of the input to the SVM was 118. The classifier was able to reduce this number to 9.44 (92% reduction) with a 77.4% sensitivity, at a 95% confidence interval of (0.71, 0.84).

Fig. 4. FROC curve of SVM performance, demonstrating 77.4% sensitivity at 9.44 FP per case, with a 95% confidence interval of (0.71, 0.84).

6. RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the results of the detections. The feature filter eliminates some obviously false candidates, such as detections outside the disk and very small detections (5b)). The SVM classifier further eliminates false candidates, such as the overly bright detection in the left pedicle (5c)). The SVM classifier does fail to classify some detections as false positives. Examples of this such as failure of initial erosion, relative intensity contrast to intervertebral space, and osteophytes, are shown in Figures 5 d)-f). In this case the SVM operating point was .24 (50% sensitivity). Figure 5g) shows an example of 3D detections of the CAD system, and 5h) is the same as 5g) with the ground truth lesions superimposed.

7. CONCLUSION

We have presented a computer-aided detection system for detecting sclerotic metastatic bone lesions of the spine on CT studies.

In contrast to previous work on lytic bone lesions [2], this project brings up the challenges of overmerging in three dimensions. Moreover, sclerotic lesions tend to be less homogeneous and less isolated than lytic lesions, and there are generally more lesions present in a single clinical case. We address this increased complexity by training SVM's on 3-D features and imposing additional constraints (overlap and intensity) during the merging into three dimensions.

This CAD system has potential to increase the sensitivity for initial detection of sclerotic metastatic lesions in the spine, as well as in assessment of bone tumor burden in cases of known sclerotic bone metastases. Future work could include software extension for sclerotic lesion detection in other bones, such as the pelvis and the ribs (both of which can demonstrate complex architectural appearance on CT cross-sectional imaging and potential suboptimal lesion detection), as well as to sclerotic lesions of alternate etiology such as infection and insufficiency fractures.

Fig. 5. Detection results. a) Original image. Green arrow denotes true lesion. b) After feature filter. Green shaded detections have passed through the feature filter, whereas red shaded detections were filtered out (red arrows). c) After SVM classification. Purple arrow denotes false detection eliminated by SVM. d)-f): False positive detections missed by SVM. Second row shows original images, third row shows detections (green) and ruled-out detections (red). d) FP in the cortical border missed by the initial erosion. e) Relative intensity contrast to intervertebral space. f) Osteophyte. g) 3D detections. h) 3D detections with ground truth lesions superimposed. Green line segments show detections corresponding to ground truth lesions.

8. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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9. REFERENCES

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